

ISic0635

I.Sicily inscription 0635

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

sandstone

Object

altar

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

2006.04; 2013.09.30

Last Change

2020-12-21 - Jonathan Prag made minor edits

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Viale Teocrito, 1955-56 (by an individual living on the adjoining via Socrate)

Coordinates

37.075435, 15.282962

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 66947

Physical Description

A small horned altar, with a square hollow in the top and a moulded base. The moulding is damaged around the front of the base, and the horns are chipped, but it is otherwise only lightly worn. The reverse is entirely plain.

Dimensions

Height 11 cm

Width 12.5 cm

Depth 10 cm

Layout

The inscribed field is 9.5 cm wide and 5.3 cm high

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

The letters are somewhat irregular and unevenly spaced, and do not closely follow the incised guidelines. Sigma is lunate, but epsilon is quadrate

Letter heights:

Line 1-2: 7-14 mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: not measured mm

Text

1. Γ(άϊος) · Κλαύδιος

2. εὐχάν

Apparatus

Text from autopsy

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 644877

PHI 332965

Bibliography

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Photo J. Prag, Aut. Assessorato Beni Culturali Regione Siciliana n.10681 del 06/05/2014